

Review on fuzzy water quality index for surface water with artificial neural network

Sarita Jibhau Wagh*, G. M. Ponde and M. D. Sangale

*P.V.P.College, Pravaranagar, S.P.P.University, Pune, Maharashtra, 413713, India. *email:saritawagh1986@gmail.com*

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Abstract

Our water quality is still being impacted by human activity, which is a big issue on a global scale. Since the 1960s, the worldwide state of surface water and groundwater systems' overall water quality has been determined using a critical water quality index (WQI) technique. This analysis will aid in choosing a water quality index model to assess the quality of water used for drinking, irrigation, residential usage, and industrial use. Monitoring the quality of groundwater around drilling sites is essential for safeguarding water supplies. The acquired characteristics were used to calculate the index for water quality. The goal of this review is to evaluate how well Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approaches can simulate the groundwater water quality index. A multiple regression model was used to produce the seven ANN input parameters that were optimized and constrained. The optimal parameters (electrical conductivity, pH, calcium, magnesium, and sodium ions) were determined for a network with five input neurons in addition to five neurons in the hidden layer. Thus, especially in industrial settings, neural network models may be utilized to directly forecast the quality of groundwater. This suggested approach, which makes use of cutting-edge artificial intelligence, can help with water management and treatment.

Key words: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Canadian Council of Minister environment (CCME), Fuzzy Water Quality Index (FWQI), Water Quality Index (WQI).

Introduction

For drinking, farming, and industrial uses, groundwater is primarily used by people ^{1,2}. Therefore, it is essential to fully comprehend the geochemical processes that control the chemical composition of groundwater since doing so will help us better understand the hydrochemical systems in many parts of the world ³. By highlighting the connections between groundwater quality, aquifer lithology, and recharge type, such information can also help with groundwater resource management and exploitation ^{4,5}. Surface water and groundwater systems are viewed as two distinct entities in traditional approaches to managing water resources; however, recent advances in the analysis of land and water resources have shown that both systems have an impact on one another from both a qualitative and quantitative perspective ^{6,7}. However, groundwater pollution caused by anthropogenic activities or by the natural material makeup of aquifers lowers the capacity of groundwater supplies or restricts their use ^{8,9}. Although other geological and anthropogenic activities can also affect groundwater quality ^{10,11}, since it is a component of physical and chemical parameters that are impacted by human and geological activities ¹²⁻¹⁴, agricultural activities such as the use of fertilizers and pesticides may also have an impact on groundwater quality. The traditional method of analyzing the quality of groundwater often relies heavily on mathematical modelling techniques such as time series analysis, probability statistics, etc. The overall accuracy of these models is typically low since these approaches presuppose that the dependent and independent variables have a linear relationship ^{15,16}. There is a need for fresh computational methods to this topic given the ongoing difficulties in modelling groundwater quality ^{17,18}. Over the past 10 years, the development of AI models in the hydrological and environmental fields has drawn enormous interest ¹⁹⁻²³. In this context, several researches have concentrated

on the development of computer methods for simulating groundwater quality. For instance, Yesilnacar *et al.* ²⁴ created an artificial neural network (ANN) model to forecast the concentration of nitrate in groundwater in Turkey's Harran Plain. The developed model succeeded in achieving a cost-effective management of groundwater resources. The complicated nonlinear interactions between the assessment component and the grade of the water quality were also resolved by the ANN technique. The model also obtained a high degree of prediction accuracy and gave a workable and reasonable performance as an assessment method. For the purpose of predicting groundwater sulphate (SO₄) and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) concentrations, Yesilnacar and Sahinkaya ¹⁵ created an ANN model. Using the suggested strategy might make managing groundwater resources easier and more affordable. The ANN modelling approach, which is based on statistical analysis, may be used to estimate the water content of soils under a variety of climatic situations.

Azimi *et al.* ²⁵ provided ANN and modified fuzzy clustering models for assessing changes in drinking water quality. On actual examples of the southeast aquifers in Iran's central area, the models' performance was assessed. When compared to earlier reports, the study revealed that the updated clustering strategy might increase the model's prediction accuracy.

Material and Methods

Water quality indicators: Input variables used for water quality index are given in Tables 1 and 2.

A. Physical indicators: Temperature, electrical conductivity, taste, total suspended solids (TSS), turbidity, odor, color, total dissolved solids (TDS)

B. Chemical indicators: pH, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD),

Table 1. Input variables used for water quality index.

Year	Test Object	Input (Variable)	Source
2021	Drinking water	pH, T-Alk, T-Hard, DO, TS, MPN	Patki <i>et al.</i> ²⁶
2021	Drinking water (India)	DO, pH, EC, BOD, N-NO ₃ , Fecal Coliform, Total Coliform	Al-Adhaileh <i>et al.</i> ²⁷
2021	Drinking water distribution (India)	TDS, N-NO ₂ ⁺ , N-NO ₃ ⁻ , Ca, Mg, Na, K, Cl ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻ , HCO ₃ ⁻ , F ⁻ , pH, TH, SAR, RSC	Vijay <i>et al.</i> ²⁸
2021	River (India)	pH, DO, BOD, Turbidity, TS	Nayak <i>et al.</i> ²⁹
2018	River (Ethiopia)	TSS, NO ₃ , NO ₂ , T-N, T-Alk, TOC, COD, BOD, DO, T, EC, pH	Yilma <i>et al.</i> ³⁰
2012	River (Malaysia)	pH, EC, TDS, NTU, WT, BOD, DO, N-NH ₃ , Mg, Cl, F, TH, Fe, Zn, As, Total Coliform, <i>E coli</i> , SS, N-NO ₃	Gazzaz <i>et al.</i> ³¹

Table 2. Parameter for Water Quality Index according to BIS Standard Report 1991 ³².

Sr. No	Parameter	Standard Method
1	Ammonium (NH ₄)	Standard Methods - Distillation-Nesslerization
2	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Chromotropic Acid Method
3	Total Organic Carbon (TOC)	Oceanography International Method
4	Alkalinity (as CaCO ₃)	Titrimetric - Methyl Orange Endpoint Method
5	Hardness (as CaCO ₃)	EDTA Titration Method
6	Chloride (Cl)	Mohr Method (Titrimetric w/AgNO ₃)
7	Conductivity (TFR)	Wheatstone Bridge
8	Total Filtrable Residue (TFR)	Residue on evaporation at 180°C
9	Total Filtrable Residue (TFR)	Residue on evaporation at 104°C
10	Nonfiltrable Residue (NFR)	Standard Method at 104°C
11	Ortho Phosphorus	Plus Hydrolyzable Phosphate, Dissolved - as Phosphorus
12	Total Iron (Fe), Total Manganese (Mn), Na, Cu, Zn	Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry
13	Turbidity	Nephelometric (Hach Turbidimeter)
14	Dissolved Oxygen	- mg/L (YSI - meter)
15	pH	pH Meter
16	Temperature	A mercury Thermometer
17	Electrical Conductivity	EC Meter

chemical oxygen demand (COD), dissolved oxygen (DO), total hardness, phosphate, pesticides, nitrate, surfactants, heavy metals

C. Biological indicators: Some biological indicators are used for water quality measurement such as bacteria (fecal coliform, *Escherichia coli*, *Cryptosporidium*, *Giardia lamblia*), viruses, fungi, protozoa, parasitic worms (*Pimephales promelas*), Trichoptera or caddisfly, sea urchin, mollusca.

Water Quality Index: The WQI converts water excellence factor stages into a statistical mark using scientific tools, illuminating the typical condition of water physiquess. It is examined from the standpoint of how humanoids will be used. Based on physical, chemical, and biological factors, WQI may be evaluated. The purpose of the idea of water is to categorise water according to the degree of concentration ³³. The process of scoring that provides the total strength of each individual water excellence component over water excellence is discussed. The WQI is calculated to evaluate the survey region's groundwater's suitability for drinking purposes. Indian Standards' recommended measurements for drinking: 10500. The weighting for several water quality parameters in this method is anticipated to differ from the suggested measurements for the resulting factors ³⁴. Thus, the following approach is used to calculate the value of the *i*th factor:

$$W_i = k / s_i \quad (1)$$

where, W_i is the unit weight for the *i*th parameter, s_i the recommended standard for the *i*th parameter and $i=1,2,3,\dots,16$; and k the constant of balance.

The estimate includes next stages:

(a) Computation of quality score for individual water excellence factors

(b) Mean of sub-indicators in over-all index

The quality score is offered:

$$Q_i = 100 * V_i / S_i \quad (2)$$

where, v_i is precise cost of *i*th factor in groundwater test under concern, s_i , allowable threshold for the *i*th factor.

WQI describes:

$$WQI = \sum (Q_i W_i) / \sum W_i \quad (3)$$

The processed WQI estimates are organized into 5 types (Table 3).

Table 3. Category of WQI value.

Water Excellence	WQI Values
Excellent	<50
Good	50-100
Poor	100-200
Very poor	200-300
Unfit	>300

Fuzzy Water Quality Index: A professional technique with a focus on rules is the fuzzy expert approach. Fuzzy logic is used as a tool to demonstrate several types of intelligence on the conundrum (Fig.1). The measurement of drinking water quality uses fuzzy logic³⁵. Data on physical, chemical, and biological aspects may be used to evaluate the water quality of any given area or resource. The excessive quantities of the aforementioned components are

Figure 1. Fuzzy Expert System.

dangerous to a person's physical health. A novel method for estimating water quality uses "fuzzy-logic" to combine many issues. It provides a more exact assessment of general quality ³⁶. *FWQI with six input variables*. The plan's results include giving the best intake water, which is disseminated to 4 further types ³⁷. The membership functions planning the semantic variables define the intelligence ground illuminating the system's performance ³⁸. Hence, for the proposed system's behavior, 7 semantic variables are identified. Out of these 6, six is input variables namely- turbidity (T), dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOC), pH value (pH), Nitrate (NO₃) and Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) and one is output variable drinking water quality. Each point in the input space is justified in its evolution through the application of triangle and trapezoidal membership functions, which are connected to a membership cost between 0 and 1 ³⁹. This expert system goes through three stages: fuzzification, evaluation of the inference rules, and defuzzification of the output findings. If-then rules are used to construct inferences. The if-part of an if-then rule is referred to as the antecedent, and the then-part is referred to as the consequent. Fuzzification is used to characterize inputs, outputs, and the unique membership function of each ⁴⁰. Two or more membership values from fuzzified input variables are used as the input to the fuzzy operator ⁴¹. Each of the seven input factors is divided into several groups in this study.

The crisp collection is modifying which called fuzzy set. It allows just complete association or no association at the whole and fuzzy sets allow limited association ⁴². In a crisp collection, membership or non-membership of element x in set A is described by a characteristic function $\mu_A(x)$, where $\mu_A(x)=1$ if $x \in A$ and $\mu_A(x)=0$ if $x \notin A$. Fuzzy set theory extends this concept by defining partial membership. A fuzzy set A on a universe of discourse U is characterized by a membership function $\mu_A(x)$ that takes values in the interval $[0, 1]$. Commonsense language terms like slow, quick, tiny, huge, heavy, low, middle, high, and tall are represented by fuzzy sets ⁴³. At any given time, an element can be a part of several fuzzy sets. In essence, a membership function is a curve that specifies how each point in the input space is translated to a membership value (or degree of membership) ranging from 0 to 1. Depending on the model option, the number scale and association function outline are chosen. The level of accuracy needed in the output amount. The formula to choose the membership function is as follows.

$$f(m; p, q, r) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } m < p \\ \frac{m-p}{q-p} & \text{for } p \leq m < q \\ \frac{r-m}{r-q} & \text{for } q \leq m \leq r \\ 0 & \text{for } m > r \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Trapezoidal arcs vary according to 4 factors $p, q, r,$ and s .

$$f(m; p, q, r, s) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } m < p \\ \frac{m-p}{q-p} & \text{for } p \leq m < q \\ 1 & \text{for } q \leq m < r \\ \frac{s-m}{s-r} & \text{for } r \leq m < s \\ 0 & \text{for } s \leq m \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The most elementary crisp set operations are union, intersection, and complement, which essentially correspond to OR, AND, and NOT operators, respectively. Let P and Q be two subsets of M . The union of P and Q , denoted $P \cup Q$. That is, $\mu_{P \cup Q}(x)=1$ if $x \in P$ or $x \in Q$. The intersection of P and Q , denoted $P \cap Q$, contains all the elements that are simultaneously in P and Q ; that is, $\mu_{P \cap Q}(x)=1$ if $x \in P$ or $x \in Q$. The complement of P is denoted by \bar{P} , and it contains all elements that are not in P ; that is $\mu_{\bar{P}}(x)=1$ if $x \notin P$, and $\mu_{\bar{P}}(x)=0$ if $x \in P$. In FL, the truth of any statement is a matter of degree. To define FL operators, AND, OR, and NOT operators are to be used. The answer is min, max, and complements operations. These operators are defined by Equation (6),(7) and (8) respectively.

$$\mu_{P \cup Q}(x) = \max[\mu_P(x), \mu_Q(x)] \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_{P \cap Q}(x) = \min[\mu_P(x), \mu_Q(x)] \quad (7)$$

$$\mu_{\bar{P}}(x) = 1 - \mu_P(x) \quad (8)$$

Fuzzy inference systems consist of if-then rules that specify a relationship between the input and output fuzzy sets. Fuzzy relations present a degree of presence or absence of association or interaction between the elements of two or more sets. U_o , is then calculated as the average of the individual centroids, weighted by their heights as given by Equation (9)

$$U_o = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N u_i \mu(u_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N \mu(u_i)} \quad (9)$$

The processed FWQI estimates are organized into 11 types (Table 4).

Table 4. Fuzzy Water Quality Index.

Water Excellence	FWQI Values
More than Excellent	1
Excellent	0.9
Very Good	0.8
Good	0.7
Fair	0.6
Average	0.5
Bad	0.4
Poor	0.3
Very Poor	0.2
Not Fit	0.1
Not Acceptable	0

Canadian Council Water Quality Index: In 2001, the CCME WQI received support. Since 2001, the CCME WQI has been widely used in Canada and other countries to report on the quality of the water supply ⁴⁴. The CCME WQI has also undergone extensive testing and evaluation by many researchers throughout the years. This User's Manual was created utilising the initial CCME WQI development effort as well as additional information learned after 2001. The Technical Report (2001) and the User's Manual, two CCME papers, have been updated by this User's Manual ⁴⁵.

The Alberta Agricultural Water Quality Index and the British Columbia Ministry of Environment, Lands and Parks' respective indexes serve as the foundation for the CCME WQI and are quite similar to each other. The technique for computing one element related to amplitude, which is detailed below, is the main distinction between the original index and the CCME WQI.

The CCME WQI is based on a combination of three factors:

1. Number of parameters whose guidelines are not met (Scope)
2. Frequency with which the guidelines are not met (Frequency),
3. Amount by which the guidelines are not met (Amplitude).

These are combined as the summation of the three vectors (scope, frequency and amplitude) to produce a single value between 0 and 100 that describes water quality

The CCME WQI is simple to compute and versatile enough to be applied in a number of circumstances ⁴⁵. The index can be used to compare sites directly or to track changes in water quality over time at a specific site. However, comparisons will be less accurate if the criteria and standards used by different sites to create the index vary. The processed CCME WQI estimates are organized into 5 types (Table 5).

Table 5. CCME Water Quality Index.

Water Excellence	CCME WQI Values
Excellent	95-100
Good	80-94
Fair	65-79
Marginal	45-64
Poor	0-44

Horton Water Quality Index: For the evaluation of fresh surface waters, the Horton model has been employed by several researchers in numerous different nations. The four conventional WQI components—parameter selection, sub-index computation, parameter weighting, and sub-index aggregation—are present ⁴⁶. Choosing a parameter eight physicochemical water quality measures, including DO, pH, coliforms, specific conductance (precise total dissolved solids measured specifically), carbon chloroforms extract, alkalinity, and chlorides, were used in the original Horton model ⁴⁷. Based on the input of the percentage of the population serviced by treatment upstream, the model additionally incorporated sewage treatment as a metric for assessment. Important environmental factors, such as parameter importance, the relative effect of other parameters, and the validity and dependability of the data, were taken into account while determining the model's parameters ⁴⁷. Generation Sub-index Horton used a linear scaling function to translate parameter values to the sub-index, and sub-index values were allocated based on the pollution condition or concentration level. The sub-index

values ranged from 0 to 100, with 100 being the highest possible recommendation for excellent conditions. When treatment facilities are operational and serve almost the whole upstream population (95 to 100 percent), with a direct, observable impact at the site under consideration, a value of 100 is assigned to the sewage treatment sub-index. A zero value is used if 50% of the population is being serviced. The population serviced is subsequently taken into account when grading rating values that fall between specified restrictions ⁴⁵.

The Delphi method was used to determine the parameter weight values. When assigning weight values, environmental importance and relative consequences were taken into account. The different water quality metrics were given weight ratings by the expert panel ranging from 1 to 4. For four parameters (special conductivity, chlorides, alkalinity, and carbon chloroform extract), Horton offered 1, 2, and 4, respectively. For one parameter (faecal coliforms), Horton proposed 2 and (DO, sewerage treatment and pH)

An additive function is used to aggregate the final WQI value as follows:

$$HWQI = \left[\frac{w_1s_1 + w_2s_2 + \dots + w_ns_n}{w + w_2 + \dots + w_n} \right] m_1m_2 \quad (10)$$

where m_1 and m_2 are the coefficients of temperature and obvious pollution, respectively.

The processed HWQI estimates are organized into 5 types (Table 6).

Table 6. Horton Water Quality Index.

Water Excellence	HWQI Values
Very Good	91-100
Good	71-90
Poor	51-70
Bad	31-50
Very Bad	0-30

Discussion

Artificial Neural Network Water Quality Index Model: ANNs were used to predict WQI using the Neural Net-work library in the MatLab and Simulink computing environments. The multiple regression analysis was used to determine the number of input parameters. The physicochemical parameters EC, pH, Ca, Mg, PO4-P, K, seven input neurons, and the output neuron—WQI—were the model's inputs ⁴⁸. Then, the stepwise regression approach was used to evaluate the models with progressively fewer variables. The Levenberg-Marquardt method was used for training and the Neural Network Fitting software was used for modelling⁴⁹. The system employed a two-layer feed-forward network with linear output neurons and sigmoid hidden neurons ⁵⁰. There was a hidden layer in the networks. The literature claims that networks with more hidden layers are better suited for scenarios of greater complexity ⁵¹. The mean square error and the regression value R scores were taken into account while choosing the number of neurons in the hidden layer. 70% of the data were from the training set, and 15% each from the test and validation sets. Fig.2 depicts a schematic representation of the ANN for the first model ⁵².

Two measures of network quality were employed—mean square

Table 7. Comparison of Water Quality Index Models.

WQI Model	Parameters	Category of result	Types of Parameter Use	Drawback	Benefit
WQI	13	5	Physical, Chemical, Biological	Less Accuracy	Simple Processing
FWQI	10	10	Physical, Chemical, Biological	More Time	More Classes
CCME WQI	4	5	Chemical	Model does not specify the WQ parameter	Less Time
Horton WQI	8	5	Chemical	No Nutrient elements for the WQ	Additional Parameter consider in WQI like Temperature and Obvious Pollution
ANN WQI	7	Correlation value	Physical, Chemical, Biological	Complex in Design	More Accurate and Less Time

Figure 2. Artificial Neural Network.

error (MSE) and regression R-value⁵³. MSE was calculated from the Equation (11):

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i' - y_i^*)^2 \quad (11)$$

The regression coefficient R⁵⁴ measures the correlation between outputs and inputs and is derived from the Equation (12):

$$R(y^l, y^*) = \frac{\text{cov}(y^l, y^*)}{\sigma_{y^l} \sigma_{y^*}} \quad (12)$$

In order to compare the quality of WQI predictions for individual models, the root mean square error (RMSE) indicator will be used (Eq. 13), calculated as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE} \quad (13)$$

Comparison of Water Quality Index Models is given in Table 7.

Conclusions

In this review process, the Artificial Neural Network WQI(ANNWQI) model is best model for water quality index as compared to WQI, FWQI, CCME, Horton model. The ANNWQI is working on the physical, chemical and biological parameter. In this model, on the basis of minimum parameter, water quality is easily determined. The accuracy of water quality is increasing due to correlation within parameter. In this model, number of parameters can be increased easily, but in other model number of parameter is constraint for determination of water quality. The ANN model is reducing the cost of lab work due to correlation of parameter values. The ANNWQI can determine the accurately water quality on the basis of key water quality parameter so no need to analysis other parameter.

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